

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1980	Davor Džalto	1998	2006			Serbian Yugoslav artist, art historian, theologian and liberal philosopher	
1980	David Zbiral	2001	2008			Czech Associate Professor, Study of Religions	
1980	Anders Engberg-Pedersen	2002	2012			Danish Associate Professor of Comparative Literature	
1980	Krzysztof Pijarski	2002	2012			Polish art historian, translator, and photopainter	
1980	Kate Bowler	2002	2010		w	Canadian associate professor of the history of Christianity in North America	
1980	Adam Mearns	2003	2003			British Lecturer in the History of the English Language	
1980	Akira Omaki	2003	2010			American linguist	
1980	Amaranth Borsuk	2004	2010		w	American Assistant Professor, School of Interdisciplinary Arts and Sciences (poet known for her experiments with textual materiality and digital poetry)	
1980	Anton Karl Ingason	2004	2016			Icelandish linguist	
1980	Aseel Abdulateef Taha	2004	2012		w	Iraqi assistant Professor in English literature	
1980	Mari Uusküla	2004	2008		w	Estonian Professor of Linguistics and Translation Theory	
1980	Michał Németh	2004	2011			Polish linguist	
1980	James S. Bielo	2004	2007			American socio-cultural anthropologist, specializing in the Anthropology of Religion, the Anthropology of Christianity, American Religion, Urban Anthropology, Linguistic Anthropology, and the study of Material Religion	
1980	Cèsar Favà Monllau	2005	2018			Spanish art historian	
1980	Nina Spicijarić Paškvan	2005	2013		w	Croatian linguist	
1980	Saada Bader	2005	2010		w	Jordanian Clinical linguist (Phonetics and Phonology)	
1980	Jue Ren	2005	2014			Chinese (Hong Kong) researcher in Gender Studies	
1980	Mónica Aguilar Bonilla	2005	No		w	Costa Rican Professor of Archaeology and Anthropology	
1980	Edward Dutton	2005	2005			British English anthropologist	
1980	Anamaria Tomiuc	2006	2011		w	Romanian Associate Professor within the History and Theory of Art	

1980	Ieva Garda-Rozenberga	2006	2012	w	Latvian researcher in Folklore and Art (Sociology, Anthropology, and Folkloristics)
1980	Tommaso Caselli	2006	2009		Italian Assistant Professor, Faculty of Arts
1980	Jelena Ilić Plauc	2006		w	Bosnian Associate Professor of English Linguistics
1980	Azra Bešić	2006		w	Bosnian Associate Professor of English Linguistics
1980	Deema Ammari	2007	2007	w	British-Jordanian Assistant Professor of English Literature (Feminism, Colonial Studies, Modern Literature, Cultural Studies)
1980	Marwa Ghazi Mohammed	2007	2017	w	Iraqi Asst. Prof. of English Literature (English Literature, modern and American theatre)
1980	Tanja Trška	2007	2014	w	Croatian Senior Research Assistant, Department of Art History
1980	Nastasă, Ionut Gabriel	2007	No		Romanian assistant professor at the Faculty of Orthodox Theology in Iași and conductor of the Men's Choir "Metropolitan Iosif Naniescu"
1980	Meltem Turan Eroğlu	2007		w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1980	Lukas Pokorny	2007	2008		Austrian Professor of Religious Studies
1980	Dr. Rika Astari, SS, MA	2008	2008	w	Indonesian lecturer in Arabic linguistics at Center of Arabic Letters
1980	Jason Lepojärvi	2008	2015		Finnish and Canadian Assistant Professor of Religious Studies
1980	Ana Ostroški Anić	2009	2015	w	Croatian researcher of Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics
1980	Shintaro Miyazaki	2009	2012		Swiss-Japanese senior researcher and principal investigator at the Institute of Experimental Design and Media Cultures
1980	Toms Ķencis	2009	2012		Latvian researcher in Folklore and Art (disciplinary history, cultural nationalism, and comparative analysis of verbal charms)
1980	Emilija Potevska	2009	2013	w	North Macedonian Professor of Music Art
1980	Bianca Williams	2009	2009	w	American Black American cultural anthropologist, feminist, author and academic
1980	Siska Yuniati	2009		w	Indonesian writer, editor, outstanding blogger, language teacher, and civil apparatus at the Ministry of Religion

1980	Bilal Orfali	2009	2009		Lebanese scholar of Arabic language and literature	
1980	Jelena Danilovic	2010	2014	w	Serbian assistant professor at the English department of the Faculty of Philology and Arts	
1980	Jelena Danilović	2010	2014	w	Serbian linguist and educator (vocabulary, morphology, L2 acquisition)	
1980	Fredrick Acheampong	2010	No		Ghanaian PhD Candidate in Religious Studies	
1980	Asko Nivala	2010	2015		Finnish Postdoctoral Researcher, Cultural History and European and World History	
1980	Mandana Yousefi	2011	2013	w	Iranian researcher of Department of English Language	
1980	Anna Swartwood House	2011	2011	w	American Assistant Professor of Art History	
1980	Zahra Sadeghi	2012	2017	w	Iranian Lecturer of English Literature	
1980	Sinan Ayyıldız	2012	2018		Turkish Assistant Professor on musicology, singer, composer	
1980	Feriyal Aslam	2012	2012	w	Pakistani social-cultural anthropologist, peace ambassador and Bharat Natyam classical dancer	
1980	Juan Martin Vives	2012	2015		Argentinian Director, Center for Studies on Law and Religion	1980-2019
1980	Dr. Ahmad Abdel Tawwab Sharaf Eldin	2013	2013		Egyptian linguist (english)	
1980	Rasha Maqableh	2013	2013	w	Jordanian assistant professor of English Literature at the Department of English Literature and Language	
1980	Stig Andreassen	2013	No		Norwegian MBA Digital Culture	
1980	Nicolaus Janos Raag	2013	2016		Swedish Postdoctoral position at Department of Modern Languages	
1980	Oluwatoyin Adebola Gbadamosi	2013	2018		Nigerian Lecturer of Philosophy of Religion	
1980	Pimsiri Taylor	2014	2014	w	Thai linguist	
1980	Marina Novina	2014	2018	w	Croatian Assistant Professor of Philosophy	
1980	Ibrahim Saweros	2015	2016		Egyptian Lecturer of Coptic Studies	
1980	Michał Szostak	2017	2019		Polish concert organist, organologist, musicologist and researcher	
1981	Vlatko Ilić	2002	2010		Serbian Assistant Professor, Faculty of Dramatic Arts	

1981	Nathan T. Elkins	2003	2010		American Associate Professor of Art History (Greek and Roman art, coinage and coin iconography, topography and architecture, sport and spectacle, and the illicit antiquities trade)
1981	Dafne Muntanyola-Saura	2004	2008	w	Spanish sociologist (ethnography of artistic settings, such as dance, filmmaking and visual arts)
1981	Martijn Wieling	2004	2012		Dutch Professor of linguistics with information science and statistics
1981	Toon Van Hal	2004	2008		Belgian Postdoctoral fellow (history of linguistics, Greek and comparative linguistics, and general history (early modern era))
1981	Igor Leturia	2005	2010		Spanish Project Manager, Language Technology
1981	Ioana Măgureanu	2005	2012	w	Romanian Assistant Professor in art history, National University of Arts
1981	J. Pilapil Jacobo	2005	2011		Philippino Assistant Professor of Literature
1981	Johann-Mattis List	2005	2013		Germanish linguist
1981	Rait Rosin	2005	2019		Estonian practising artist and scholar of pragmatist philosophy
1981	Shah Nishant	2005	2013		Indian professor of new media
1981	Zoltan Somhegyi	2005	2010		Hungarian art historian
1981	Kirsten Bos	2005	2012	w	Canadian physical anthropologist
1981	Ana-Maria Demetrian	2005		w	Romanian Senior Lecturer of Department of Applied Modern Languages
1981	Zarfa Hrnjić Kuduzović	2005		w	Bosnian Assistant Professor of Communicology
1981	Muhamad Isna Wahyudi	2005			Indonesian Judge of Religious Courts
1981	Adrian Hermann	2005	2011		German Professor of Religion and Society
1981	Tedi Kholiludin	2005			Indonesian lecturer at the Faculty of Islamic Religion
1981	Anna Felicia Sanchez	2006	No		Philippino lecturer literature and creative writing
1981	Anu Põldsam	2006	2011	w	Estonian Lecturer in Jewish Studies, School of Theology and Religious Studies
1981	Андрей Царенок	2006	2019		Ukrainian culturologist (патристика, аскетика, релігієзнавство, історія філософських вчень, патристична естетика)

1981	Віталіна Василівна Тарасова	2006	2010	w	Ukrainian Associate Professor of the Department of Foreign Languages of the Chemical and Physical Faculty
1981	Marco Derks	2006	2019		Dutch Executive Secretary, Netherlands School for Advanced Studies in Theology and Religion
1981	Jan Reichstätter	2006	2019		Czech doctor, Religious studies
1981	Csaba Maczelka	2007	2014		Hungarian Assistant Professor of English Literature
1981	Mirjana Mirić	2007	2016	w	Serbian Research Associate of Institute for Balkan Studies (linguistics)
1981	Lina Gergova	2007	2009	w	Bulgarian assistant of (national festivity, cultural heritage, urban studie,s nationalism, migrations)
1981	Bima Slamet Raharja	2008	No		Indonesian Lecture and Researcher of Javanese Literature
1981	Daniel Graziadei	2008	2017		Germanish Assistant professor of Romance Literature
1981	Ernst van den Hemel	2008	2011		Dutch postdoctoral research fellow at the Center for the Humanities (religion and literature)
1981	Gopal Joge	2008			Indian assistant professor in Indian Art (religion)
1981	Hemanga Dutta	2008	2011		Indian Assistant Professor of Linguistics
1981	Joy Dangora Erickson	2008	2019	w	American assistant professor of language arts and literacy
1981	Mirjana Crnić Novosel	2008	2015	w	Croatiam postdoctoral researcher of The Institute of Croatian language and linguistics
1981	Benedikt Paul Göcke	2008	2011		German Research Fellow, Ian Ramsey Centre for Science and Religion
1981	Jasmina Hanić	2009	2011	w	Bosnian professor of Department of English Language and Literature, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
1981	Hafza Girdap	2009		w	Turkish researcher in Women's and Gender Studies
1981	Fabrizio Boscaglia	2010	2015		Italian Researcher in Portuguese Literature and Philosophy
1981	Yongsheng Chen	2010	2010		Chinese Lecturer of Chinese linguistics
1981	András Suki	2010	2014		Hungarian piano teacher
1981	Mohammad Awad Al.Dawoody	2011	2015		Egyptian Lecturer of linguistics
1981	Joan Lee Tu	2011	No		Canadian linguist and data scientist (text messaging)

1981	Abdullah AlBadarneh	2012	2012		Jordanian Professor of English Literature
1981	Dr. Sultan Alhatmi	2012	2012		Saudi Arabian Assistant professor of applied linguistics
1981	Amin Honarmand	2012	2012		Iranian Associate Professor of Music
1981	Dr. Felix Ayioka Orina	2013	2014		Kenyan Lecturer of Literature
1981	Mary-Ann Ochota	2013	No	w	British broadcaster and anthropologist specialising in anthropology, archaeology, social history and adventure factual television
1981	Finaflor Taylan	2014	No	w	Philipino Professor of Social Work and Women
1981	Onyeka Uzuegbu	2014	No		Nigerian graduate of English language & literary studies
1981	Ingus Barovskis	2015	2015		Latvian researcher in Literature, Latvian folklore, mythology, modern mythology and life stories
1981	Nazanin Mousavi	2016	No	w	Iranian writer, researcher in Persian language and literature
1982	Gayatri Reddy	2000	2000	w	Indian anthropologist who has also made contributions to queer and gender studies
1982	Nedim Begović	2002	2014		Bosnian Professor of Islamic Jurisprudence (fiqh) and Religion and Law
1982	Maja Znika Marion	2003	2015	w	Croatian Assistant, Institute for Croatian Language and Linguistics
1982	Gerrit Jan Kootstra	2004	2012		Dutch psycholinguistics of multilingualism and language acquisition
1982	Jeana Jorgensen	2004	2012	w	American folklorist, writer, dance, and sex educator
1982	Jānis Oga	2004	2014		Latvian Acting Researcher (literature studies, comparative literature, cultural studies, soviet colonialism and post-colonialism, non-violent resistance)
1982	Edin Jasarovic	2004	2016		Montenegrin Producer at Faculty of Dramatic Arts
1982	Martin John Callanan	2005	No		British conceptual artist (researching an individual's place within systems)
1982	Molly Babel	2005	2009	w	Canadian linguist
1982	Наталья Федина	2005	2010	w	Russian philologist (Языкознание, тюркские языки, грамматика, морфология, фонетика)
1982	Asadu Emmanuel Uzoma	2006	No	w	Nigerian Graduate assistant of Department English & Literary Studies

1982	Pieter Boulogne	2006	2010		Dutch Assistant Professor of Russian Literature, translator
1982	Andrew P. Klager	2006	2011		Canadian Director – Institute for Religion, Peace and Justice
1982	Julio Villa-García	2007	2012		Spain professional linguist
1982	Katarina Žeravica	2007	2014	w	Croatian Assistant Professor, Academy of Arts
1982	Kun Akaabir	2007	No		Indonesian anthropologist (Islamic Studies, Diaspora, Social Sciences)
1982	Eugenia Battisti	2007	2010	w	Italian art historian
1982	Ryan Hartigan	2008	No		New Zealand Associate Professor of Theater (artist, director and performer of theatre)
1982	Selma Veseljević Jerković	2008	2012	w	Bosnian Professor of English Language and Literature (popular culture and literature, Young Adult literature, women's writing)
1982	Sergi Domenech Garcia	2008	2013		Spanish art historian
1982	Jordan Randall Smith	2008	No		American conductor, arts entrepreneur, and percussionist
1982	Amarnath Amarasingam	2008	2013		Sri Lankan-Canadian Assistant Professor, School of Religion
1982	Timothy J Furry	2008	2011		American Instructor of Religion and Philosophy
1982	Andy Pramono	2009	No		Indonesian lecturer of art and design
1982	Eman Abdou	2009	No	w	Egyptian Lecturer in the Painting department, faculty of Fine Arts (visual painting)
1982	Dmitri Leontjev	2010	2016		Estonian postdoctoral researcher in Applied Linguistics
1982	Ana Penjak	2010	2013	w	Croatian researcher in literature (Literature, Identity)
1982	Mohamad Faizuan Mat	2011	No		Malaysian lecturer in the Fine Arts Programme (fine arts, visual arts)
1982	Noli Maishara Nordin	2011	No	w	Malaysian Lecturer of English Language at Academy of Language Studies
1982	Tessa Eka Darmayanti	2012	No	w	Indonesian researcher in art and design
1982	Hasan Hadi Abu-krooz Al-Ka'abi	2012	2018		Iraqi Professor of Pragmatics
1982	Kenan Kösemehmetoğlu	2012	No		Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages

1982	Eshqane Babayeve	2013	2013	w	Azerbaijani researcher of Institute of Literature (turkish literature)
1982	Rich Perks	2013	2013		British Lecturer in Music Performance
1982	Yair Haendler	2014	2017		German-Israeli linguist
1982	Shivan Toma	2014	2016		Iragi linguist
1982	Othman Abualadas	2015	2015		Jordanian Assistant Professor of Linguistics and Translation Studies
1982	Ajose, Toyin Samuel	2017	No		Nigerian Lecturer, Department of Music
1983	Ivaylo Markov	2003	2011		Bulgarian ethnologist (migration, borderlands, cultural heritage, identities, local development)
1983	Dusanka Popovic	2006	2014	w	Montenegrin Professor of Language and Literature
1983	Jelena Gledic	2006	No	w	Serbian Senior Instructor of Faculty of Philology
1983	Mirela Berbić-Imširović	2006		w	Bosnian Associate Professor at the Department of Bosnian Language and Literature
1983	Adrian Stoleriu	2007	2012		Romanian visual artist (Sacred Art)
1983	Arup Majumder	2007	2015		Indian anthropologist of School of Languages and linguistics
1983	Verita Sriratana	2007	2013	w	Thai Assistant Professor, Department of English, Faculty of Arts
1983	Екатерина Сергеевна Палеха	2007	2007	w	Russian philologist (лингвокриминология, лингвистическая экспертиза, психолингвистика)
1983	Verita Sriratana	2007	2013	w	Thai Assistant Professor, Department of English, Faculty of Arts
1983	Gregory Tate	2008	2009		British Lecturer in Victorian Literature
1983	Kee-Man Chuah	2008	No		Malaysian Academic & Researcher (cognitive linguistics, technology-enhanced learning, assistive technology and learning analytics)
1983	Martin Schweinberger	2008	2014		Austrian Postdoctoral Research Fellow in Language Technologies
1983	Jasmina Đonlagić	2008	2014	w	Bosnian Assistant professor of Department of German language and literature
1983	Mart Kuldkepp	2008	2014		Estonian Scandinavianist, historian and translator
1983	Astrid Lorange	2009	2014	w	Australian writer, editor, and artist
1983	Beibei Xu	2009	2017		Chinese linguist

1983	Francesca Di Garbo	2009	2014	w	Italian linguist (Classics and Historical Linguistics, gender studies)
1983	Sandya Maulana	2010	2016		Indonesian lecturer of Department of Literature and Cultural Studies (science fiction)
1983	Irina Andreea Stoleriu	2010	2012	w	Romanian art historian
1983	Ramona Hârşan	2010	2013	w	Romanian Assistant Professor (Senior Lecturer) in Literature (Literature, Cultural Studies, and Romanian Literature)
1983	Umami Hani Abu Hassan	2011	2018	w	Malaysian lecturer of malay literature
1983	Malik Kareem Hassoun	2011	No		Iraqi Lecturer in Linguistics/Pragmatics
1983	Rita Anne McNamara	2012	2016	w	American Lecturer in Cross-Cultural Psychology
1983	Travis Brisini	2012	2012		American Professor in the Communication Arts (Performance theory, Posthumanism, Environmental Humanities, Multispecies Studies)
1983	Yasser Issa Al-Shboul	2012	2014		Jordanian linguist
1983	Chidoo Ezika	2012	No		Nigerian Lecturer 2 in Translation and Interpreting, Morphology and Cultural Studies
1983	Mamatov Ulugbek Nasimovich	2012	No		Uzbeki Teacher researcher (Culturology, Fine art, Philosophy, History)
1983	Julia Spichal	2012	2014	w	Austrian assistant professor of Religion
1983	Julia Valle Noronha	2013	2019	w	Brazilian Associate Professor at Estonian Academy of Arts (fashion designer-researcher)
1983	Barnali Chetia	2013	2013	w	Indian Assistant Professor (Linguistics)
1983	Willy Himawan	2013	No		Indonesian Lecturer, Visual Art Department, Asian Modern & Contemporary painter
1983	Afifa Afrin	2013	No	w	Bangladeshi Gender Analyst
1983	Zoe Todd	2013	2017	w	Canadian Métis anthropologist and scholar of Indigenous studies, human-animal studies, science and technology studies and the Anthropocene
1983	Bengü Cilalı	2014	No	w	Turkish Instructor of Department of Modern Languages
1983	Asst. Prof. Dr. Çelen Dimililer	2016	2017	w	Turkish Associate Professor of English Language Teaching
1983	Anne Greeley	2016	2017	w	American Associate Professor of Art History

1983	Marijana Janjić	2016	No	w	Croatian Indologist and Croatist, she researches Indian languages, especially Hindi, and Croatian as a foreign and second language
1984	Nataliia I. Melnyk	2004		w	Ukrainian educator (педагогічні науки, компаративістика, лінгвістика, філологія)
1984	Borko Baraban	2005	2015		Croatian Senior teaching assistant at the Chair in Cultural Studies (history of Croatian language, especially in the 19th and 20th century)
1984	Francesca Medaglia	2005	2013	w	Italian Lecturer (RTDA) in Comparative Literature
1984	Ivana Brač	2006	2017	w	Croatian Research assistant of Institute of Croatian Language and Linguistics
1984	Egil Asprem	2006	2012		Norwegian Associate professor (docent) in the history of religions
1984	Klaas Coulembier	2007	2013		Dutch self-employed freelance musicologist, graphic designer, composer
1984	Pauls Daija	2007	2013		Latvian literary scholar
1984	Risimati Hobyane	2007	2012		South African Doctor of Ancient Languages
1984	Abdel Rahman Mitib Altakhaineh	2008	2016		Jordanian Assistant Professor of English Language and Linguistics
1984	Lovro Škopljanac	2008	2013		Croatian Research Associate at Department of Comparative Literature
1984	Sebastian Lory (né Sulger)	2008	2015		German computational linguist
1984	Olga Kaczmarek	2008		w	Polish anthropologist and Holocaust educator
1984	Alenka Jelovšek	2009	2014	w	Slovenian linguist
1984	Koenraad Claes	2009	2011		Belgian lecturer in Romantic period literature 19st century
1984	Ricardo José Barbieri	2009	2016		Brazilian anthropologist
1984	Xinying Chen	2009	2012	w	Chinese researcher at Department of Czech Language
1984	Šejn Husejnefendić	2009			Bosnian Assistant Professor at Department of Journalism
1984	Philipp Öhlmann	2009			German Head of Research Unit Religious Communities and Sustainable Development

1984	Katy McKinney-Bock	2010	2013	w	American Research Associate at Center for Spoken Language Understanding
1984	Nela Hasanbegović	2010	No	w	Bosnian member of the Association of Visual Artists of Bosnia and Herzegovina (sculptor)
1984	Andreas Serafim	2010	2013		Cypriot Postdoctoral Fellow in Classics (Ancient Greek, Oratory Rhetoric, Performance, Persuasion, Public speaking)
1984	Jo-Marí Schäder	2010	No	w	South African Lecturer of Ancient Languages and Cultures
1984	Marco Donnarumma	2011	2016		Italian performance artist, new media artist and scholar
1984	Vihanga Perera	2011	No		Sri Lankan Research Student in Literature (published poet, short story writer and novelist)
1984	Peyo Karpuzov	2011	No		Bulgarian Lecturer of Literature and English
1984	Laura M. Holzman	2012	2012	w	American art historian (Public art, visual studies, museum studies, local culture, tourism, memory)
1984	Amy Mihyang Ginther	2012	No	w	American Korean-born Assistant Professor of Theater Arts
1984	Antonia Ordulj	2012	2016	w	Croatian Research Assistant and University Lecturer in Croatian as Second and Foreign Language
1984	Miroslav Kubát	2013	2015		Czech assistant professor at Department of Czech Language
1984	Felipe Cervera	2013	2018		Mexican theatre and performance maker, lecturer and researcher at LASALLE College of the Arts
1984	Sumaya Haj	2013	2016	w	Palestinian Assistant Professor of English Literature (English Literature, Postcolonial Literature, Feminism, Cultural Studies, Caribbean Literature)
1984	Aleah N. Ranjitsingh	2013	2015	w	Trinidadian Adjunct Assistant Professor in the fields of Women and Gender Studies, Caribbean Studies and Africana Studies
1984	Kate McMahon	2013	2017	w	American Researcher & Exhibition Development, Center for the Study of Global Slavery
1984	Waliya, Yohanna Joseph	2013	No		Nigerian Faculty member of Modern Languages and Translation
1984	Ishak Tekin	2013	No		Turkish Assistant Professor, Religious Education

1984 Kingsley Uwaegbute	2013	No		Nigerian assistant Lecturer, DEPARTMENT OF RELIGION AND CULTURAL STUDIES
1984 Jānis Ozoliņš	2014	2016		Latvian researcher of Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art (Narrative theories, prose rhetoric, cognitive poetics, gender studies, masculinity studies, contemporary Latvian literature (from the mid-1980s to the present), film history and theory)
1984 Mufleh Alqahtani	2014	2014		Saudi Arabian Associate Professor in Theoretical Linguistics (Phonology)
1984 Gentiana Muhaxhiri	2014	2014	w	Albanian Assistant of Albanian Literature
1984 Fabio Ander Lete López	2014	No		Spanish Antropologist
1984 Basim Jubair Kadhim	2015	2019		Iraqi Lecturer of Linguistics
1984 Belma Šarančić Nahodović	2015	2015	w	Bosnian Associate Professor, Music academy
1984 Revital Madar	2015	No	w	Israeli Doctorate student, The Cultural Studies Program
1984 Alolaiwi Hayder Naji Shanbooj	2016	2018		Iraqi researcher in American Literature, former Ministry of Education
1984 Nerma Pezerović-Riđić	2016		w	Bosnian senior assistant of Department of English Language and Linguistics